

Intramolecular Diels-Alder Reactions of Pyrano[4,3-*b*]-indol-3-ones. Preparation of [*c*]-Annulated Carbazoles^ψ

CHRISTOPHER J. MOODY* and ANDREW I. MORRELL

Department of Chemistry, Loughborough University of Technology, Loughborough, Leicestershire, LE11 3TU, U K

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The pyrano[4,3-*b*]indol-3-ones (**5**), readily prepared from *t*-butyl indole-2-acetate (**2**) in three steps, undergo facile intramolecular Diels-Alder reaction on heating to give, after loss of carbon dioxide, the [*c*]-annulated carbazoles (**6**).

Over the last few years, we¹⁻⁵ and others⁶⁻¹⁰ have been interested in the synthesis of carbazole derivatives using the Diels-Alder reaction of the indole-2,3-quinodimethane diene system. Thus we have described the preparation of simple carbazoles¹⁻⁴ and of the carbazole alkaloids carbazomycin A and B, and hyellazole³ using this methodology. More recently we have prepared the more complex alkaloid staurosporinone using the intramolecular variant of the reaction⁵. In continuation of these studies, we now report the application of the intramolecular Diels-Alder reaction of pyranoindolones to the synthesis of [*c*]-annulated carbazoles, where the fused ring is an oxygen containing heterocycle.

Results and Discussion

The substrates **5** for the intramolecular Diels-Alder reaction were prepared from *t*-butyl indole-2-acetate (**2**) readily available from 2-nitrophenylacetic acid in 64% overall yield as shown in Scheme 1. The choice of the *t*-butyl ester,

Scheme 1 Reagents: (i) (COCl)₂, CH₂Cl₂, (ii) Meldrum's acid, ¹Pr₂NEt, CH₂Cl₂, (iii) *t*-BuOH, reflux, (iv) TiCl₃, acetone, ammonium acetate buffer

as opposed to the ethyl ester that we used in earlier work^{4,5}, was crucial in that it allows the differentiation between two ester groups at a later stage in the synthesis (q.v.).

The desired side-chain was introduced into the 3-position of the indole ring by reaction with oxalyl chloride^{5,11}, followed by quenching of the intermediate with an alkynol. Four alkynols (propargyl alcohol, 2-butyne-1-ol, 3-butyne-1-ol and 3-pentyne-1-ol) were used, and gave the corresponding glyoxylates (**3a-d**; 46-73% yield) (Scheme 2). The *t*-butyl ester was cleaved selectively using *p*-toluenesulphonic acid (PTSA) in benzene to give the acids (**4**) in excellent yields (79-99%), cyclodehydration of which using acetic anhydride gave the desired pyranoindolones (**5**) (Scheme 2).

The intramolecular Diels-Alder reaction (Scheme 3) was carried out by heating the pyranoindolones either in boiling bromobenzene (**5a** and **5b**) or neat in the melt (**5c**), and gave the desired [*c*]-annulated carbazoles (**6a-c**) in modest yields. No carbazole was obtained on heating the pyranoindolone (**5d**); only decomposition occurred.

Experimental

Commercially available solvents and reagents were used throughout without further purification, except for those detailed below which were purified

^ψDedicated to Professor D. P. Chakraborty in recognition of his outstanding contribution to the chemistry of carbazole alkaloids.

Scheme 2. [a, $n = 1$, $R = H$; b, $n = 1$, $R = Me$. c, $n = 2$, $R = H$; d, $n = 2$, $R = Me$].
 Reagents : (i) $(COCl)_2$, ether, then $HO(CH_2)_n-C \equiv CR$, (ii) PTSA, benzene, reflux, (iii) Ac_2O , THF, room temperature.

as described. 'Light petroleum' refers to the fraction of petroleum ether boiling between 40 and 60°, and was distilled through a 36 cm Vigreux column before use. Diethyl ether, benzene and toluene were dried where necessary by standing over sodium wire for several days. THF was distilled from sodium benzophenone ketyl under

Scheme 3

nitrogen, prior to use. Dichloromethane was distilled from phosphorus pentoxide. Amines were distilled from, and stored over, potassium hydroxide pellets. Methanol and ethanol were distilled from magnesium turnings and iodine, and stored over activated 4A molecular sieves under nitrogen.

Analytical thin layer chromatography was carried out using aluminium backed plates coated with Merck Kieselgel 60 GF254. Plates were visualised under uv-light (at 254 and/or 360 nm) or by staining with phosphomolybdic acid reagent, followed by heating. Flash chromatography was carried out using Merck Kieselgel 60 H silica or Matrex silica 60. Pressure was applied at the column head with hand bellows. Samples were applied pre-adsorbed on silica or as a saturated solution in an appropriate solvent.

Infrared spectra ($CHCl_3$, thin film or KBr) were recorded in the range 4 000–600 cm^{-1} using a Nicolet FT-205 spectrometer, with internal calibration. 1H and ^{13}C nmr spectra were recorded using Bruker AC-250 and Bruker WH-400 (SERC NMR Spectroscopy Centre, Warwick) instruments. High and low resolution mass spectra were recorded on a Kratos MS80 instrument or on a VG Analytical ZAB-E instrument (SERC Mass Spectrometry Service, Swansea). Melting points were measured on an Electrothermal digital melting point apparatus and are uncorrected. Elemental analyses were carried out on a Perkin-Elmer 2400 analyser.

t-Butyl 4-(2-nitrophenyl)-3-oxobutanoate (**1**) : Oxalyl chloride (6.14 ml, 70 mmol) was added dropwise to a stirred solution of 2-nitrophenylacetic acid (10.6181 g, 58 mmol) in dichloromethane (200 ml). The resulting solution was stirred at room temperature for 1 h and the solvent was then removed under reduced pressure. The residue was redissolved in dichloromethane (200 ml) and a solution of Meldrum's acid (9.1900 g, 64 mmol) and diisopropylethylamine (22.12 ml, 127 mmol) in dichloromethane (100 ml) was added. The reaction mixture was poured into water (100 ml) and the organic layer was separated, washed with

hydrochloric acid (1M; 50 ml), brine (50 ml) and dried (MgSO₄). The residue was dissolved in *t*-butanol (200 ml) and the resulting solution was refluxed for 2 h. The solvent was removed under reduced pressure and the residue was chromatographed (ethyl acetate) to give compound **1** (16.2559 g, 99%), m.p. 74–76° (Found : $M + NH_4^+$, 297.1450. C₁₂H₂₁N₂O₅ requires : 297.1450); ν_{max} (KBr) 2 980, 1 740, 1 720, 1 612, 1 578, 1 524, 1 410, 1 346, 1 260, 1 152, 1 030, 958, 866, 790, 730, 700 and 674 cm⁻¹; δ_H (250 MHz; CDCl₃) 1.49 (9H, s), 3.54 (2H, s), 4.25 (2H, s), 7.29–7.32 (1H, m), 7.43–7.50 (1H, m), 7.57–7.63 (1H, m), 8.10–8.14 (1H, m); m/z 237 ($M + NH_4^+$, 100%), 280 (9), 241 (100), 223 (44), 206 (17), 197 (14), 146 (24), 120 (14), 74 (8).

t-Butyl indole-2-acetate (**2**) : A solution of *t*-butyl 4-(2-nitrophenyl)-3-oxobutanoate (**1**; 4.1724 g, 15 mmol) in acetone (30 ml) was shaken vigorously with 15% aqueous titanium trichloride solution (110 ml) and ammonium acetate solution (4M, 375 ml) for approximately 10 min. The resulting dark green solution was extracted with diethyl ether (3 × 25 ml). The combined organic extracts were dried (MgSO₄) and the solvent was removed under reduced pressure. The residue was chromatographed to give compound **2** (2.2569 g, 65%), m.p. 114–16° (Found : M^+ , 231.1259. C₁₄H₁₇NO₂ requires: 231.1259); ν_{max} (KBr) 3 392, 3 084, 3 056, 2 980, 1 724, 1 618, 1 584, 1 550, 1 490, 1 454, 1 424, 1 370, 1 342, 1 328, 1 288, 1 030, 930, 872, 786 and 748 cm⁻¹; δ_H (250 MHz; CDCl₃) 1.48 (9H, s), 3.73 (2H, d, J 0.7 Hz), 6.31 (1H, m), 7.03–7.17 (2H, m), 7.31–7.34 (1H, m), 7.52–7.55 (1H, m), 8.72 (1H, bs); m/z 231 (M^+ , 25%), 175 (51), 130 (100), 103 (14), 89 (3), 77 (15), 57 (31), 41 (18).

t-Butyl[3-propargyloxy]glyoxylyl]indole-2-acetate (**3a**) : Oxalyl chloride (0.34 ml, 3.9 mmol) was added dropwise to a solution of *t*-butyl indole-2-acetate (600 mg, 2.6 mmol) in diethyl ether (25 ml) at 0°. The resulting solution was stirred for 15 min and propargyl alcohol (0.23 ml, 3.9 mmol) was then added. The reaction mixture was

stirred at room temperature for 1 h and poured into water (25 ml). The organic layer was separated and washed with saturated sodium bicarbonate solution (25 ml) and brine (25 ml). The ether layer was dried (MgSO₄) and the solvent removed under reduced pressure. The residue was chromatographed (dichloromethane) to afford compound **3a** (652 mg, 73%), m.p. 104–06° (Found : M^+ , 341.126. C₁₉H₁₉NO₅ requires : 341.126); ν_{max} (evaporated film) 3 292, 1 739, 1 735, 1 719, 1 628, 1 458, 1 269 and 1 152 cm⁻¹; δ_H (250 MHz; CDCl₃) 1.52 (9H, s), 2.59 (1H, t, J 2.4 Hz), 4.23 (2H, s), 5.00 (2H, d, J 2.4 Hz), 7.2–7.29 (2H, m), 7.39–7.44 (1H, m), 7.83–7.87 (1H, m), 10.68 (1H, bs); m/z 341 (M^+ , 17%), 286 (32), 202 (86), 174 (100), 158 (29), 129 (29), 102 (16) and 57 (69).

t-Butyl 3-[(2-butyn-1-oxy)glyoxylyl]indole-2-acetate (**3b**) : Oxalyl chloride (0.12 ml, 1.35 mmol) was added dropwise to a solution of *t*-butyl indole-2-acetate (312 mg, 1.35 mmol) in diethyl ether (10 ml) at 0°. The resulting solution was stirred for 15 min and 2-butyn-1-ol (0.20 ml, 2.7 mmol) was then added. The reaction mixture was stirred at room temperature for 1 h and poured into water (10 ml). Work-up as above gave compound **3b** (251 mg, 53%), m.p. 112–14° (Found : M^+ , 355.1420. C₂₀H₂₁NO₅ requires : 355.1419); ν_{max} (evaporated film) 3 301, 1 737, 1 634, 1 490, 1 457, 1 369, 1 333, 1 270, 1 240, 1 153, 1 113, 970 and 748 cm⁻¹; δ_H (250 MHz; CDCl₃) 1.52 (H, s), 1.90 (3H, t, J 2.4 Hz), 4.24 (2H, s), 4.66 (2H, q, J 2.4 Hz), 7.20–7.29 (2H, m), 7.38–7.43 (1H, m), 7.83–7.86 (1H, m), 10.64 (1H, bs); m/z 355 (M^+ , 8%), 300 (15), 202 (90), 174 (100), 158 (25), 129 (27), 102 (8) and 57 (65).

t-Butyl 3-[(3-butyn-1-oxy)glyoxylyl]indole-acetate (**3c**) : Oxalyl chloride (0.39 ml, 4.5 mmol) was added dropwise to a solution of *t*-butyl indole-2-acetate (693 mg, 3.0 mmol) in diethyl ether (25 ml) at 0°. The resulting solution was stirred for 15 min and 3-butyn-1-ol (0.34 ml, 4.5 mmol) was then added. The reaction mixture was stirred

at room temperature for 1 h and poured into water (25 ml). Work-up as above gave compound **3c** (634 mg, 60%), m.p. 113–15° (Found : M^+ , 355.1420. $C_{20}H_{21}NO_5$ requires : 355.1419); ν_{\max} (evaporated film) 3 368, 1 733, 1 704, 1 691, 1 562, 1 488, 1 455, 1 369, 1 327, 1 290, 1 251, 1 149, 1 117, 1 077, 1 066 and 746 cm^{-1} ; δ_H (250 MHz; $CDCl_3$) 1.50 (9H, s), 2.29 (1H, d, J 2.2 Hz), 2.67 (2H, m), 4.16 (2H, s), 4.50 (2H, t, J 6.9 Hz), 7.18–7.25 (2H, m), 7.33–7.38 (1H, m), 7.75–7.81 (1H, m), 10.66 (1H, bs); m/z 355 (M^+ , 11%), 202 (100), 174 (56), 158 (84), 130 (22), 102 (13), 77 (10), 57 (40), 41 (66) and 27 (22).

t-Butyl 3-[(3-pentyn-1-oxy)glyoxylyl]indole-2-acetate (**3d**) : Oxalyl chloride (0.20 ml, 2.2 mmol) was added dropwise to a solution of *t*-butyl indole-2-acetate (345 mg, 1.5 mmol) in diethyl ether (15 ml) at 0°. The resulting solution was stirred for 15 min and then 3-pentyn-1-ol (0.20 ml, 2.2 mmol) was added. The reaction mixture was stirred at room temperature for 1 h and poured into water (15 ml). Work-up as above gave compound **3d** (258 mg, 46%), m.p. 119–21° (Found : M^+ , 369.1576. $C_{21}H_{23}NO_5$ requires : 369.1576); ν_{\max} (evaporated film) 3 277, 1 735, 1 719, 1 702, 1 638, 1 534, 1 490, 1 458, 1 369, 1 332, 1 272, 1 245, 1 166, 1 114, 1 027 and 747 cm^{-1} ; δ_H (250 MHz; $CDCl_3$) 1.52 (9H, s), 1.73 (3H, t, J 2.6 Hz), 2.62 (2H, m), 4.24 (2H, s), 4.47 (2H, t, J 7.0 Hz), 7.21–7.28 (2H, m), 7.38–7.343 (1H, m), 7.75–7.79 (1H, m), 10.62 (1H, bs); δ_C (62 MHz; $CDCl_3$); m/z 369 (M^+ , 7%), 202 (80), 174 (45), 158 (100), 129 (12), 102 (8), 77 (8), 57 (25), 41 (44) and 27 (7).

3-[(2-Propyn-1-oxy)glyoxylyl]indole-2-acetic acid (**4a**) : *p*-Toluenesulphonic acid (20 mg, 0.1 mmol) was added to a solution of the ester (**3a**; 649 mg, 1.9 mmol) in benzene (25 ml). The resulting solution was refluxed for approximately 2 h and then poured into saturated sodium bicarbonate solution (25 ml). The organic layer was separated and washed with saturated sodium bicarbonate solution (2 × 25 ml). The

combined aqueous extracts was acidified with hydrochloric acid (1M) and extracted with ethyl acetate (3 × 25 ml). The combined organic extracts was washed with brine (10 ml), dried ($MgSO_4$) and the solvent removed under reduced pressure. The residue was chromatographed (ethyl acetate) to afford compound **4a** (539 mg, 99%), m.p. 152–54° (Found : M^+-CO_2 , 241.0740. $C_{14}H_{11}NO_3$ requires : 241.0739); ν_{\max} (KBr) 3 293, 1 735, 1 724, 1 719, 1 702, 1 620, 1 461, 1 275, 1 247, 1 174 and 745 cm^{-1} ; δ_H (250 MHz; $(CD_3)_2CO$) 1.52 (9H, s), 1.73 (3H, t, J 2.6 Hz), 2.62 (2H, m), 4.24 (2H, s), 4.47 (2H, t, J 7.0 Hz), 7.21–7.28 (2H, m), 7.38–7.344 (1H, m), 7.75–7.79 (1H, m), 10.62 (1H, bs); m/z 241 (M^+-CO_2 , 6%), 158 (100), 130 (15), 103 (10), 77 (10), 63 (3) and 51 (4).

3-[(2-Butyn-1-oxy)glyoxylyl]indole-2-acetic acid (**4b**) : The ester (**3b**; 388 mg, 1.09 mmol) was treated as above to give compound **4b** (307 mg, 94%), m.p. 160–62° (Found : M^+-CO_2 , 255.0895. $C_{15}H_{13}NO_3$ requires : 255.0898); ν_{\max} (KBr) 3 319, 1 738, 1 733, 1 717, 1 618, 1 460, 1 269, 1 247, 1 170, 1 120, 975 and 748 cm^{-1} ; δ_H (250 MHz; $(CD_3)_2CO$) 1.68 (3H, t, J 2.3 Hz), 4.26 (2H, s), 4.97 (2H, q, J 2.3 Hz), 7.19–7.29 (2H, m), 7.53–7.57 (1H, m), 7.88–7.91 (1H, m), 11.52 (1H, bs); m/z 269 (M^+-CO_2 , 68%), 158 (100), 130 (87), 103 (56), 77 (52), 65 (18) and 53 (22).

3-[(3-Butyn-1-oxy)glyoxylyl]indole-2-acetic acid (**4c**) : The ester (**3c**; 60 mg, 0.17 mmol) was treated as above to give compound **4c** (40 mg, 79%), m.p. 161–63° (Found : MH^+-CO_2 , 256.0974. $C_{15}H_{14}NO_3$ requires : 256.0974); ν_{\max} (KBr) 3 292, 1 735, 1 619, 1 490, 1 458, 1 272, 1 245, 1 170 and 748 cm^{-1} ; δ_H (250 MHz; $(CD_3)_2CO$) 2.46 (1H, t, J 2.6 Hz), 2.71 (2H, m), 4.27 (2H, s), 4.50 (2H, t, J 6.7 Hz), 7.21–7.29 (2H, m), 7.53–7.57 (1H, m), 7.88–7.91 (1H, m); m/z 255 (M^+-CO_2 , 29%), 158 (100), 130 (35), 103 (21), 89 (4), 77 (21), 63 (4), 53 (10), 44 (12) and 39 (9).

3-[3-Pentyn-1-oxy]glyoxylyl]indone-2-acetic acid (4d) : The ester (**3d**; 237 mg, 0.64 mmol) was treated as above to give compound **4d** (183 mg, 91%), m.p. 167–69° (Found : M^+ -CO₂, 269.1052. C₁₆H₁₅NO₃ requires : 269.1052); ν_{\max} (KBr) 3 289, 1 738 1 621, 1 617, 1 490, 1 459, 1 269, 1 238, 1 168 and 748 cm⁻¹; δ_{H} (250 MHz; (CD₃)₂CO) 1.71 (3H, t, *J* 2.6 Hz), 2.63 (2H, m), 4.27 (2H, s), 4.38 (2H, t, *J* 6.7 Hz), 7.20–7.29 (2H, m), 7.52–7.59 (1H, m), 7.85–7.90 (1H, m), 10.77 (1H, bs); *m/z* 269 (M^+ -CO₂, 67%) 158 (100), 130 (87), 103 (56), 89 (11), 77 (52), 65 (18) and 53 (16).

*Propargyl 3-oxopyrano[4,3-*b*]indole-1-carboxylate (5a)* : Acetic anhydride (5 ml, 53 mmol) was added to a stirred solution of the acid (**4a**; 352 mg, 1.2 mmol) in tetrahydrofuran (5 ml). The reaction mixture was stirred for 2 h at room temperature and then the solvent was removed under reduced pressure. The residue was triturated with diethyl ether to give compound **5a** (299 mg, 91%), m.p. 250°d (Found : M^+ , 267.0530. C₁₅H₉NO₄ requires : 267.0531); ν_{\max} (KBr) 3 449, 3 306, 3 142, 1 743, 1 737, 1 692, 1 669, 1 644, 1 619 1 459, 1 386, 1 295, 1 278, 1 266, 1 176, 1 151, 1 107 and 755 cm⁻¹; δ_{H} (250 MHz; (CD₃)₂CO) 2.62 (1H, t, *J* 2.4 Hz), 5.10 (2H, d, *J* 2.4 Hz), 5.89 (1H, s), 7.15–7.24 (1H, m), 7.29–7.35 (1H, m), 7.29–7.39 (1H, m), 8.71 (1H, m), 10.65 (1H, bs); *m/z* 267 (M^+ , 29%), 223 (15), 194 (22), 184 (100), 166 (14), 156 (7), 139 (8), 128 (62), 101 (28), 75 (17), 63 (8) and 51 (13).

*2-Butynyl 3-oxopyrano[4,3-*b*]indole-1-carboxylate (5a)* : Acetic anhydride (5 ml, 53 mmol) was added to a stirred solution of the acid (**4b**; 67 mg, 0.2 mmol) in tetrahydrofuran (5 ml). The reaction mixture was stirred for 2 h at room temperature and then the solvent was removed under reduced pressure. The residue was triturated with diethyl ether to give compound **5b** (64 mg, 98%), m.p. 251°d (Found : M^+ , 281.0690. C₁₆H₁₁NO₄ requires : 281.0688.); ν_{\max} (KBr) 3 438, 1 730, 1 694, 1 667, 1 641, 1 619,

1 586, 1 461, 1 385, 1 295, 1 268, 1 179, 1 150 and 1 110 cm⁻¹; δ_{H} (250 MHz; (CD₃)₂SO) 1.89 (3H, t, *J* 2.4 Hz), 5.06 (2H, q, *J* 2.4 Hz), 5.98 (1H, s), 7.14–7.27 (2H, m), 7.46–7.52 (1H, m), 8.56–8.59 (1H, m), 11.53 (1H, s); *m/z* 281 (M^+ , 6%), 237 (7), 208 (10), 184 (100), 144 (3), 128 (14), 119 (3), 101 (8), 77 (6), 53 (7) and 45 (4).

*3-Butynyl 3-oxopyrano[4,3-*b*]indole-1-carboxylate (5c)* : Acetic anhydride (5 ml, 53 mmol) was added to a stirred solution of the acid (**4c**; 35 mg, 0.1 mmol) in tetrahydrofuran (5 ml). The reaction mixture was stirred for 2 h at room temperature and then the solvent was removed under reduced pressure. The residue was triturated with diethyl ether to give compound **5c** (32 mg, 98%), m.p. 250°d (Found : MH^+ , 282.0766. C₁₆H₁₂NO₄ requires : 282.0766); ν_{\max} (KBr) 3 450, 3 304, 3 148, 1 722, 1 688, 1 655, 1 641, 1 619, 1 460, 1 298, 1 278, 1 266, 1 182, 1 153 and 755 cm⁻¹; δ_{H} (250 MHz; (CD₃)₂CO) 2.50 (1H, t, *J* 2.7 Hz), 2.79 (2H, m), 4.58 (2H, t, *J* 6.8 Hz), 5.96 (1H, s) 7.14–7.23 (1H, m), 7.27–7.33 (1H, m), 7.30–7.40 (1H, m), 8.67 (1H, m), 10.45 (1H, bs); *m/z* 282 (MH^+ , 10%), 238 (100), 186 (11), 172 (6), 160 (6), 144 (10), 132 (10), 100 (8), 94 (8), 70 (12), 58 (32) and 44 (96).

*3-Pentynyl 3-oxopyrano[4,3-*b*]indole-1-carboxylate (5d)* : Acetic anhydride (5 ml, 53 mmol) was added to a stirred solution of the acid (**4d**; 189 mg, 0.6 mmol) in tetrahydrofuran (5 ml). The reaction mixture was stirred for 2 h at room temperature and then the solvent was removed under reduced pressure. The residue was triturated with diethyl ether to give compound **5d** (157 mg, 88%), m.p. 247°d (Found : C, 68.77; H, 4.33; N, 4.69. C₁₇H₁₃NO₄ requires : C, 69.15; H, 4.44; N, 4.74%); ν_{\max} (KBr) 3 289, 3 152, 1 737, 1 693, 1 671, 1 644, 1 619, 1 588, 1 460, 1 386, 1 294, 1 266, 1 175 and 1 151 cm⁻¹; δ_{H} (250 MHz; (CD₃)₂CO) 1.79 (3H, t *J* 2.6 Hz), 2.64 (2H, m), 4.46 (2H, t, *J* 6.9 Hz), 6.01 (1H, s), 7.12–7.21 (1H, m), 7.26–7.31 (1H,

m), 7.28–7.37 (1H, m), 8.64 (1H, m), 10.83 (1H, bs); *m/z* 295 (M^+ , 8%), 250 (17), 184 (100), 156 (4), 144 (28), 128 (41), 115 (4), 101 (17), 91 (4), 77 (18) and 55 (22).

Dihydro-3H,6H-furo[3,4-c]carbazol-1-one (6a) : A solution of the pyranoindolone (**5a**; 23.7 mg, 0.09 mmol) in bromobenzene (10 ml) was refluxed under nitrogen for 3 h. The solvent was then removed under reduced pressure and the residue was chromatographed (dichloromethane) to give compound **6a** (15.2 mg, 76%), m.p. 285–88° (Found : M^+ , 223.0633. $C_{14}H_9NO_2$ requires : 223.0633); ν_{\max} (KBr) 3 409, 3 247, 1 733, 1 692, 1 457, 1 328, 1 297, 1 105, 1 010 and 755 cm^{-1} ; δ_H (250 MHz; $(CD_3)_2CO$) 5.52 (2H, s), 7.25–7.31 (1H, m), 7.47–7.54 (1H, m), 7.60–7.65 (1H, m), 7.95 (1H, d, *J* 8.3 Hz), 9.02 (1H, m), 10.95 (1H, bs), *m/z* 223 (M^+ , 97%), 194 (100), 166 (53), 139 (21), 83 (3) and 63 (3).

4-Methyldihydro-3H, 6H-furo[3,4-c]carbazol-1-one (6b) : A solution of the pyranoindolone (**5b**; 48.3 mg, 0.17 mmol) in bromobenzene (10 ml) was refluxed under nitrogen for 3 h. The solvent was then removed under reduced pressure and the residue was chromatographed (dichloromethane) to give compound **6b** (15.0 mg, 37%), m.p. 290–92° (Found : M^+ , 237.0790. $C_{15}H_{11}NO_2$ requires : 237.0789); ν_{\max} (KBr) 3 411, 3 237, 1 7339, 1 459, 1 451, 1 332, 1 323, 1 292, 1 140, 1 121, 1 034, 1 015, 743 and 721 cm^{-1} ; δ_H (250 MHz; $(CD_3)_2SO$) 2.45 (3H, d, *J* 0.6 Hz), 5.50 (2H, s), 7.19–7.26 (1H, m), 7.42–7.49 (1H, m), 7.55–7.59 (1H, m), 7.70 (1H, d, *J* 0.6 Hz), 8.76 (1H, dd, *J* 7.3 Hz, *J* 0.6 Hz), 11.71 (1H, bs); *m/z* 237 (M^+ , 86%), 208 (100), 180 (53), 149 (19), 105 (10), 91 (16), 83 (12), 77 (32), 69 (39) and 57 (87).

3,4-Dihydro-1H, 7H-pyrano[4,3-c]carbazol-1-one

(**6c**) : The pyranoindolone (**5c**; 9.5 mg, 0.34 mmol) was heated at 260° under nitrogen for 10 min. The residue was then chromatographed (dichloromethane) to give compound **6c** (10.0 mg, 13%), m.p. 293–95° (Found : M^+ , 237.0790. $C_{15}H_{11}NO_2$ requires : 237.0789); ν_{\max} (KBr) 3 397, 3 230, 1 696, 1 324, 1 292, 1 221, 1 134, 1 121, 1 049 and 750 cm^{-1} ; δ_H (250 MHz; $(CD_3)_2CO$) 3.19 (2H, t, *J* 5.8 Hz), 4.58 (2H, t, *J* 5.8 Hz), 7.24–7.31 (2H, m), 7.42–7.52 (2H, m), 7.61 (1H, d, *J* 8.1 Hz), 8.37 (1H, bs), 9.10 (1H, d, *J* 8.5 Hz); *m/z* 237 (M^+ , 100%), 207 (8), 179 (79), 152 (13), 89 (14), 76 (24), 69 (9), 57 (13), 43 (37).

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